

KOZEL: Kernel Organization Zappy Environment for Linux

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Abstract

This report describes application domain, design and usage of Kernel Organization Zappy Environment for Linux (KOZEL, pronounced “kazz’jol”) developed during a term project for “Expert Systems” course #CEN5120 taught by Dr. Pelin in Spring of 1997 at School of Computer Science¹, Florida International University². We present problem the system is designed to solve, discuss a conceptual view of the system architecture, give a detailed picture of its implementation and describe usage of the system.

The document is available in electronic form at <http://www.cs.fiu.edu/~beznosov/doc/kozel>.

¹<http://hpdr.cs.fiu.edu>

²<http://www.fiu.edu>

Contents

1 Introduction

Today task of configuring Operating System kernel requires not only knowledge of installed on the system hardware but also awareness of all those numerous parameters that inter-depend on each other. It is especially true with Linux³ kernel that uses the same source tree to be built on 6 different architectures as well as notebooks and laptops⁴. It is important as well to find an optimal configuration, where the kernel will contain only those parts that are really needed.

Kozel is an expert tool that allows to automate a process of Linux kernel configuration (during a building phase) by asking simple questions to a user and trying to find optimal configuration. The program can be distributed under conditions of GNU General Public License version 2 re-printed in on page 27 of this report.

The remainder of this report is organized as follows. Section 2 describes the application domain of the system. Section 3 discusses available for today solutions. Section 4 presents the proposed solution. System design is explored in Section 5. Sample session with the system is illustrated in Section 7. Conclusions are contained in Section 6. *Kozel* source code is listed in Appendix A . Distribution license the program is registered under are available in Appendix B.

2 Application Domain

Expert tool *kozel* is developed to assist in configuring Linux⁵ kernel when the kernel is built from source code. More than 300 parameters are involved in kernel configuration. They define various features of the kernel from such global characteristics as whether to build TCP/IP stack into the kernel to such miscellaneous once as Direct Memory Access channel number for a sound card.

There are dependencies among parameters. It allows for example to configure sound card DMA channel number only if a sound card is configured to be supported by the particular kernel configuration. Total parameter space is a directed graph, which is not connected.

Most of parameters define whether particular parts responsible for specific services or functionality will be built into the kernel. Those parameters can have either yes/no; yes as a module [m], or yes as a monolithic part [y], or no [n]. There are also parameters that can take integer or hexademical values. Those values are closely related to the particular hardware configuration of computer system .

3 Available Solution

Commonly accepted approach to configuration phase is a set of recursive scripts that ask a kernel configurator (further in the report *user*) to define configuration parameters or provide their values id applicable. Those scripts go from “*root*” parameters (those that do not depend on anything else) to “*leaf*” once (those who are not dependant on). For example, if a user answered “no” to CONFIG_ISDN the user will not be asked about any ISDN device.

³<http://sunsite.unc.edu/linux>

⁴<http://www.hal-pc.org/davidl/linux/linux.config.html>

⁵<http://sunsite.unc.edu/linux>

Such an approach has its advantages. It allows to behave pseudo intelligently and to eliminate many “dead routes”. It’s also simple to implement. As a matter of fact, this approach is implemented in Unix shell.

It also has tradeoffs. First is that a user has to know the whole hierarchy of parameters and define correctly those near to the root to be asked later about those further from the root. For example, if the system has PCI network card, the user has to answer “yes” somewhere at the beginning of the configuration session to the question about PCI capabilities of the computer system in general to have a chance to be asked about his/her PCI network adapter later.

Another drawback is that configuration program “talks” to the user in terms of parameters and not in terms of actual hardware available on the system and real services the operating system is supposed to provide. It is easy for a human been to get confused and to make mistakes in this case.

4 Proposed Solution

In the proposed solution, the configuration tool interviews a user about actual hardware the computer system has or will have and actual services the operating system is supposed to provide. In other words, a configuration comes from “leaf” parameters to “root” parameters. The user is asked what hardware is available on the system and what services the system will provide, and the rest is configured automatically including definition of “root” parameters that has to be defined for the system to provide required services.

4.1 Session Phases

A session of configuring a kernel consists of generating and loading dependencies into the knowledge base, interviewing a user, configuring hierarchy of parameters, and generating the result of the session. Bellow is a description of each step.

4.1.1 Loading Of Dependencies

Dependencies among paramaters are generated dynamically each time before interview with a user begins. They are extracted from the configuration scripts provided with the kernel source code.

4.1.2 Interviewing The User

Interview with the user begins when the user choses command *configure* from the main menu. During the interview the user is asked about hardware components of the system, their types and, when it is nessessary, about specific for particular hardware parameters. Example of such interview is provided in Section 7 on page 6.

4.1.3 Configuring The System

After the interview is over, the program attempts to resolve dependencies for thoses parameters that were instantiated during the previous phase. Conflicts are detected and resolved at this step as well.

4.1.4 Creating Configuration File

After all dependencies found and conflicts are resolved, the result of the session – configuration file in format acceptable by native Linux kernel building tools is generated. Below is an example of such a file:

```
CONFIG_EXPERIMENTAL=y
CONFIG_CD_NO_IDESCSI=y
CONFIG_NET_ISA=y
CONFIG_NET_ETHERNET=y
CONFIG_NETDEVICES=y
CONFIG_NET=y
CONFIG_MOUSE=y
CONFIG_BLK_DEV_IDE=y
CONFIG_PRINTER=y
CONFIG_PSMOUSE=y
CONFIG_SERIAL=y
CONFIG_INET=y
CONFIG_PPP=y
CONFIG_DEPCA=y
CONFIG_SBPCD=y
CONFIG_BLK_DEV_FD=y
CONFIG_BINFMT_JAVA=y
CONFIG_KERNEL_ELF=y
CONFIG_M586=y
```

5 System Design

Tool *Kozel* is designed as follows:

1. False driven loop *mainloop* does main menu. It prints list of possibilities and calls *get_answer/1* and *do_command/1* to recognize valid response and perform an appropriate command.
2. Service features like print list of anything, get response, make a pause are provided by *printlist/1*, *means/2*, *pause*, *get_single_char/1* and others.
3. User can ask for help and *do_help* will shed some light.
4. The system can operate in 3 modes: manual consulting, automatic consulting and conflicts resolving. Default mode is automatic and only this mode is used in a production system. Manual mode is used exclusively for debugging and test phases.

The predicates involved in dialog are *config_not_auto*, *config_linux/1*, *config/1*, *intro/1* and *define/1*. The predicate *define/1* starts definition process.

5.1 Knowledge Base

The knowledge base consists of list of dependencies among paramataers and their definitions, as well as grouping of some parameters according to the type of system hardware they define. Parameters and dependencies among them are generated automatically before each interview with the user. Groups of variables, on the other hand, are a part of knowledge base that has to be created by acquiring knowledge from a human expert.

5.1.1 Automatically Generated

List of parameters and dependencies among them is generated by a program *config2rules* (see page 22 for the program listing) written in Perl that parses configuration scripts of Linux kernel source code. The output of is loaded as a set of facts into *kozel* databases. Below is a fragment of such a database:

```
variable('IPX_INTERN', b, 'Full internal IPX network', n, undefined ).  
  
if 'IPX_INTERN' is_wanted and 'IPX' is_not n then 'IPX_INTERN'.
```

It means that parameter `IPX_INTERN` has type boolean, help message 'Full internal IPX network', and its default value is set to `n` (means no), as well as current value is `undefined`. The second line means that to set this parameter to "yes" it has to be explicitly set during an interview with the user or some other parameter (which depends on `IPX_INTERN`) should be set to "yes". Also if `IPX_INTERN` is set another parameter `IPX` should be set too.

5.1.2 Acquired From A Human Expert.

Most of kernel parameters that are mapped into system hardware components or services, has to be grouped into meaningful sets to facilitate interview with the user. The step of grouping parameters is done manually via knowledge acquisition from a human expert. Current version of system *kozel* has the following groups of parameters:

1. Hard disk types.
2. CD-ROM types.
3. Network interfaces.
4. Network connections.
5. Modem types.
6. Printer types.
7. Mouse types.
8. Tape device types.

5.2 Interview With End User

During the interview with the end user, the user is asked to choose what particular types of hardware the computer has and what types of services the operating system is supposed to provide.

The user is asked about listed above groups via predicate *ask_type_of_hardware/2*. Questions during the interview are asked via predicate *askTermD/4*.

5.3 Kernel Configuration

Manual consulting assumes that knowledge is organized in the hierarchy when kernel parameters or other atomic facts are clustered into groups and user scans hierarchy tree in a breadth search manner. So it is backward chaining meaning we start from goal “build valid configuration” and go deeper and deeper towards facts.

For each atomic parametersystem performs check if some conflicts exist in a forward chaining manner. Also, which is more valuable from the application domain point of view it sets other variables to default values whenever it found dependency from an undefined so far variable.

Predicate *resolve* starts post-configuration to find conflicts and set other variables starting from those already defined by user. It uses *resolve_var/4* to do that. Predicate *fflag/2* maintains operation mode. Automatic consulting does the same but without prompts. It uses *config_auto* as a starting point.

The consultation itself is carried out by *definevar/1*, *process_var/1*, *process_condition_of/2*, *setvar/3*, *set_variable_value/2* and *evaluate/3*.

5.4 Output Of Session Results

All parameters in the database are checked when session results are generated. If a parameter is set to some of positive values it is written into the generated output. An example of such output is shown on page ??.

6 Conclusions

Expert tool *Kozel* presents an alternative solution to a tedious and errorprone task to configure kernel of Linux operating system in right and optimal way.

7 Example of Session With The User


```

:- op(950,fx,not).
:- op(690,xfy,is).
:- op(950,xfy,is_not).
:- op(720,xfx,set_to).

%-----

% gop: just do it! (russian slang)
gop :- mainloop.

% mainloop: main false driven loop, calls a_cycle
mainloop :- repeat, a_cycle.

% a_cycle: command cycle, calls printlist, get_answer, do_command
a_cycle :-
  nl, write( 'XpertS: course project'), nl,
  printlist( ['Option List (please take one):'
    , '~~~~~'
    , '(angle brackets <> mean command argument)'
    , ''
    , 'quit          -- Exit from the program'
    , 'help          -- Find helpful information on the program'
    , 'config        -- Start configuration of the kernel'
    , 'autoconfig     -- automatically define rest of variables'
    , 'undefine       -- undefine variable or section'
    , 'load (file)    -- load knowledge base'
    , 'save (file)    -- save knowledge base'
    , '!command      -- run operating system command'
    , 'resolve        -- resolve dependecnies'
    , 'shell          -- Execute shell command'
    ]
  ), nl,
  write('Your turn: '),
  get_answer(Answer),!,
  do_command(Answer),
  !, fail.

% help facility
do_help :-
  printlist( ['This system is to configure Linux ...'
    , 'and it was developed by ...'
    , 'under provisions of ...'
    , 'and by the way, the Linux is ...'
    , 'and configuration of Linux consists of:'
    , 'a)'
    , 'b)'
    , 'c)'
    , 'd)'
    , '....'
    , 'and more help available upon request: give us a call ...'
    ]
  ), pause.

% main goal
config_not_auto :- fflag( auto, yes)
                  , retract( fflag( auto, _))
                  , fail
                  ; asserta( fflag( auto, no))
                  , config_linux.

% we just set flag and go
config_auto :- fflag( auto, no)
               , retract( fflag( auto, _))
               , fail
               ; asserta( fflag( auto, yes))
               , config_linux.

```

```

config_linux :- load_kb,
                ask_user,
                resolve,
                write_result,
                pause.

old_config_linux:-
    load_kb
    , config( general)
    , config( net)
    , config( protocols)
    , config( drivers)
    , config( misc)
.

% config procedure
% by typing anything but yes/y in response to intro
% user can skip some thing and go directly to another
config( Something) :- intro( Something)
                    , define( Something).

config( _).

% ask user if he wants to continue with this section/variable
% or proceed if autopilot on duty
% no default behaviour for auto flag assumed
intro( _ )          :- fflag( auto, yes).
intro( Something) :- fflag( auto, no),
                    printlist([ 'You are about to define'
                                , Something
                                , 'do you want to continue?'
                                ],
                                get_answer( Yesno), !,
                                Yesno == yes.

% load_kb/0 Loads knowledge base
load_kb:-
    ['linux_kernel_config.pl']
    , true.

%----- source database -----

fflag( auto, yes).
fflag( modules, yes).

% for your convenience service predicates
default_value( Var, X) :- variable( Var, _, _, X, _).
undefined( Var)      :- variable( Var, _, _, _, undefined).
hasvalue( Var, Value) :- variable( Var, _, _, _, Value)
                    , Value \== undefined.

%----- basic definition technique -----

% for process_condition_of/2 'if' clause defines branch
% case 1: unconditional setting means no dependencies: nothing to do
process_condition_of( V, Ans) :-
    if V is_wanted then V
    , Ans is 1.

% case 2: go and find out if precondition(s) satisfy or set it (them) settled
process_condition_of( V, Ans ) :-
    if V is_wanted and Cond then V
    , evaluate( Cond, y, Ans)
.

```

```

% case 3
process_condition_of( V, Ans ) :-
    if V is_wanted and Cond1 or Cond2 then V
    , evaluate( Cond1 or Cond2, y, Ans)
.

process_condition_of( _, Ans ) :- Ans is 0.
% write('by default Ans is 0 in process_condition_of'), nl.

% resolve: scans database and finds errors and contradictions
% for defined variables, it doesn't touch undefined or set to n
% assumes no more than one instance for each variable
% if you want it to stop after 1st bad case uncomment cut
resolve :- variable( Var, Vartype, _, Default, Value)
    , Value \== undefined
    , Value \== n
%
    , !
    , resolve_var( Var, Vartype, Default, Value)
.
resolve.

% resolve_var: checks if given variable ok, ie can be set by auto_setvar
% resolve_var( Var, Vartype, Default, Value) :-
resolve_var( Var, _,_,_) :-
    process_condition_of( Var, Ans)
    , !, Ans == 1
%
    , auto_setvar( Var, Vartype, Default, Value)
    , !, fail
.

% auto_setvar: determines value to be assigned by default
% yes or m for type t, yes for type b, default value for others (hex and int)
auto_setvar( Var, t, _, Val) :- fflag( modules, no), Val \== y,
    setvar( Var, y, 1).
auto_setvar( Var, t, _, Val) :- fflag( modules, yes), Val \== m,
    setvar( Var, m, 1).
auto_setvar( Var, b, _, Val) :- Val \== y, setvar( Var, y, 1).
auto_setvar( Var, _, Def, Val) :- Val \== Def, setvar( Var, Def, 1).

% definevar: defines variables via dialog mainly

% case 1: if unknown, define it
% user is asked if he wants to define this variable,
% later only valid answers will be accepted in infinite loop
definevar( V ) :- fflag( auto, no)
    , undefined( V)
    , intro( V)
    , process_var(V)
.

% case 2: automatic mode and undefined var: skip it
definevar( V ) :- fflag( auto, yes)
    , undefined( V)
.

% case 3: automatic mode and defined var: go find others
definevar( V ) :- fflag( auto, yes)
    , hasvalue( V, Value)
    , auto_process_var( V, Value)
.

% same as in config: user can skip some variables or
% system will skip already defined

```

```

% case 4: manual mode, undefined var: skip it and go for others
definevar( _).
% :- write('default for definevar '), write(V), nl.

% process_var: we consider all variables askable
% get_reply keeps asking until valid reply provided
% but process_condition_of may fail and variable remains undefined
process_var(V) :- variable( V, Vtype, Prompt,_,_)
    , express_domain( Vtype, Dom)
    , printlist( [ 'Please make your choice for'
    , V
    , 'which is'
    , Prompt
    , 'possible values are'
    , Dom
    , Dom
    ] )
    , get_reply( Ans, Vtype)
    , process_condition_of( V, Ok )
    , setvar( V, Ans, Ok)
.
process_var( _ ) :- write('default for process_var'), nl.

% auto mode for bulk processing
auto_process_var( Var, Value) :- hasvalue( Var, Oldvalue),
    printlist( [ 'This variable'
    , Var
    , 'has value'
    , Oldvalue
    , 'while should have'
    , Value
    , 'please advise... '
    ] ).

% process if evaluation succeeded
auto_process_var( Var, _ ) :-
    process_condition_of( Var, Ok)
    , !
    , Ok == 1
    , variable( Var, Vartype, __, Default, _)
    , auto_setvar( Var, Vartype, Default)
.

%----- processing conditions -----

% store variable as defined with value
setvar( V, Ans, Guard) :- Guard == 1, set_variable_value( V, Ans).

setvar( V, Ans, _ ) :- nl, write( 'Attn! variable '),
    write( V), write(' was not set to '), write( Ans), nl.

% we keep them in database
set_variable_value( Name, Value):-
    retract(variable(Name, Type, Prompt, Default, _)),
    asserta(variable(Name, Type, Prompt, Default, Value)).

% evaluate/3
% assume hasvalue/2 is opposite to undefined/1

% case 1: one variable and one value: is value OK?
evaluate( Var set_to Value, _ , Ans) :- hasvalue( Var, Value)
    , Ans is 1.

% case 2: variable is undefined, manual mode
evaluate( Var set_to Value, _ , Ans ) :- undefined( Var)
    , fflag( auto, no)

```

```

        , printlist1( [ Var
                    , 'should be defined as'
                    , Value
                    , 'press letter y and dot '
                    , 'To confirm, please'
                    ] )
        , pause
        , process_condition_of( Var, Ans)
        , setvar( Var, Value, Ans)
    .

% case 3: variable is undefined, auto mode
evaluate( Var set_to Value, _, Ans ) :- undefined( Var)
    , fflag( auto, yes)
    , process_condition_of( Var, Ans)
    , setvar( Var, Value, Ans)
.

% case 4: if value is invalid in other clauses, then complain
evaluate( Var set_to Value, y, Ans ) :-
    printlist1( [ Var
                , 'must be defined as'
                , Value
                , 'under given condition(s).'
                , 'Please advise... '
                ] )
    , Ans is 0
    , pause
.

% case 'not': var has value, either good or bad
evaluate( Var is_not Value, _, Ans ) :- hasvalue( Var, Other),
    ( Other \== Value
%           ; evaluate( Var set_to Value, Mode, Ans )
%           ; Ans is 0
    ).

% case 'not': when undefined, just set it
evaluate( Var is_not Value, Mode, Ans ) :-
    variable( Var, Typ, _, Def, undefined),
    process_condition_of( Var, Ans),
    !, Ans == 1,
    ( Typ == b, Value \== y, evaluate( Var set_to y, Mode, Ans)
    ; Typ == t, Value \== y, fflag( modules, no),
    evaluate( Var set_to y, Mode, Ans)
    ; Typ == t, Value \== m, fflag( modules, yes),
    evaluate( Var set_to m, Mode, Ans)
    ; Typ == int, Value \== Def, evaluate( Var set_to Def, Mode, Ans)
    ; Typ == hex, Value \== Def, evaluate( Var set_to Def, Mode, Ans)
    ; ask_hard_case( Var, Typ, Def, Value, Ans)
    ).

% case 'and'
% 'and' can be evaluated recursively
evaluate( Cond1 and Cond2, X, Ans ) :- evaluate( Cond1, X, Ans)
    , !, Ans ==1
    , evaluate( Cond2, X, Ans).

% case 'or'
% 'or' has different complain policy from 'and' and
% it is also different for auto and manual modes
evaluate( Cond1 or Cond2, _, Ans) :- evaluate( Cond1, nocomplain, Ans)
    ; evaluate( Cond2, nocomplain, Ans)
    ; fflag( auto, no)
    , printlist1( [ Cond1
                  , 'or'

```

```

        , Cond2
        , 'must be defined to be true.'
    ])
    , pause
    , Ans is 0
.

% weird case: ask operator
ask_hard_case( Var, Typ, Def, Value, Ans) :- write('hard_case '),
    write( Var), write( Typ),
    write( Def), write( Value),
    Ans is 0.

%----- dialog support -----
% printlist: prints list of items on the standard output
printlist(List):- clear_screen, printlist1(List).
printlist1([]).
printlist1([Item|Others]) :- nl, write(Item), printlist1(Others).

% pause: suspends and waits
pause :- nl, write('Press any key...'), ttyflush,
    get_single_char(_),
    read(_),
    nl.

% get_answer: reads user input
get_answer( Answer) :- repeat, ttyflush, read( Something),
    means( Something, Answer).

% abbreviations
means( yes, yes).
means( y, yes).
means( no, no).
means( n, no).
means( why, why).
means( w, why).
means( quit, quit).
means( q, quit).
means( help , help).
means( h , help).
means( config, config).
means( c , config).
means( autoconfig, autoconfig).
means( auto , autoconfig).
means( a , autoconfig).
means(r, resolve).
means(resolve, resolve).
means(s, shell).
means(shell, shell).
means( undefine(Var) , undef(Var)).
means( undef(Var) , undef(Var)).
means( u(Var) , undef(Var)).
% reject unknown answer
means( Answer, _) :- writef( '%w -- what?: ', [Answer]), fail.

% do_command: executes user command, calls load, find, oscommand
do_command(Ans) :- (
    Ans = quit -> halt
; Ans = help -> do_help
; Ans = load -> load_kb
% ; Ans = save(_) -> not_ready % save(File)
; Ans = resolve -> resolve
; Ans = config -> config_not_auto
% ; Ans = undef(_) -> not_ready % undef(Var)
; Ans = shell -> shell_command

```

```

).

not_ready :- write('Sorry, this feature still under construction, '),
            nl, pause.

% to help user with possible values for variables
express_domain( b, 'y or n').
express_domain( t, 'y, n or m').
express_domain( int, 'integer number or d for default').

% accept reply for variable value
get_reply( Ans, Vtype):- repeat, write(' '), ttyflush, read( A),
                        rmeans( A, Vtype, Ans).

% rmeans: y, no, m, integer or hex number are valid
rmeans( y, t, y).
rmeans( n, t, n).
rmeans( m, t, m).
rmeans( y, b, y).
rmeans( n, b, n).
% explicit number or default value if d typed in
rmeans( X, int, X) :- integer(X).
rmeans( X, hex, X).
%rmeans( d, _, X) :- ??
rmeans( _, _, _) :- write( 'What?'), fail.
%-----

% clears screen and puts cursor to the beginning of the screen
clear_screen:-
    writef('%r', ['\n',24]),
    tty_goto(0,0).

ask_user:-
    %introduction,
    assert(fflag(giving_help, n)),
    retract_ifany(fflag(quit,y)),
    general.

retract_ifany(Clause):-
    Clause,
    retract(Clause),
    fail.

retract_ifany(_).

introduction:-
    printlist([
        'You will be asked about your Linux system hardware componnets',
        'After that the program will produce configuration for your Linux kernel'
    ]),
    pause.

general:-
    set_variable_value('KERNEL_ELF', y),!,
    set_variable_value('BINFMT_JAVA', y),!,
    (
        processor_type,!,
        memory_size,!,
        floppy,!,
        disks,!,
        cdrom,!,
        network,!,
        modem,!,

```

```

        mouse,!
        printer,!
        tape,!
    )
    ;
    fflag(quit, y),
    writef('quiting...\n').

general.

%-----
processor_type:-      !,
                    writef('What processor does your computer have ?\n'),
                    askTermD('Processor Type', 386, PType_user, processor_type_help),
                    determine_processor_type(PType_user, PType),
                    string_concat('M', PType, Name),
                    assert(variable(Name, b, 'No help', n, y)).

processor_type_help:-
                    writef('Possible choises are 386, 486, Pentium, PPro\n').

determine_processor_type('Pentium', 586).
determine_processor_type(pentium, 586).
determine_processor_type('PPro', 686).
determine_processor_type(ppro, 686).
determine_processor_type(Type,Type).

%----- MEMORY SIZE -----
memory_size:-
    askTermD('How much main memory does your computer have (in MB) ?', 32, MemorySize),
    (
        MemorySize =< 16,
        set_variable_value('MAX_16M', y)
    ;
        set_variable_value('MAX_16M', n)
    ).

%----- FLOPPY -----
floppy:-
    askTermD('Does your computer have floppy ?', y, If_floppy),
    (
        If_floppy == y,
        set_variable_value('BLK_DEV_FD', y)
    ;
        set_variable_value('BLK_DEV_FD', n)
    ).

floppy.

%----- DISKS -----

disks:-
    ask_type_of_hardware(
        disk,
        hd_type2diskvariable
    ).

% Hard Drives
hd_type2diskvariable('ide', 'BLK_DEV_IDE').
hd_type2diskvariable('pcmcia', 'BLK_DEV_IDE_PCMCIA').
hd_type2diskvariable('ali_m14xx', 'BLK_DEV_ALI14XX').
hd_type2diskvariable('dtk_2278', 'BLK_DEV_DTC2278').
hd_type2diskvariable('ht6560b', 'BLK_DEV_HT6560B').

```

```

hd_type2diskvariable('dc4030', 'BLK_DEV_PROMISE').
hd_type2diskvariable('qd6580', 'BLK_DEV_QD6580').
hd_type2diskvariable('umc8672', 'BLK_DEV_UMC8672').
hd_type2diskvariable('xt', 'BLK_DEV_XD').
hd_type2diskvariable('scsi', 'BLK_DEV_SD').

%----- CD-ROM -----
cdrom:-
    ask_type_of_hardware(
        'CD-ROM',
        cdrom_type2diskvariable).

% CD-ROM disks
cdrom_type2diskvariable('goldstar r420', 'GSCD').
cdrom_type2diskvariable('matsushita', 'SBPCD').
cdrom_type2diskvariable('panasonic', 'SBPCD').
cdrom_type2diskvariable('creative', 'SBPCD').
cdrom_type2diskvariable('longshine', 'SBPCD').
cdrom_type2diskvariable('teac', 'SBPCD').
cdrom_type2diskvariable('ide_atapi', 'BLK_DEV_IDECD').
cdrom_type2diskvariable('scsi', 'BLK_DEV_SR').

cdrom_type2diskvariable('mitsumi', CD):-
    fflag(giving_help,n),
    (
        askTermD('Does it have XA/Multisession', no,
            MultSession),
        MultSession == no,
        CD is 'MCD'
        ;
        CD is 'MCDX'
        )
    ;
    true.

%-----
tape:-
    ask_type_of_hardware(
        'tape drive',
        tape_type2tapevariable).

tape_type2tapevariable(ide, 'BLK_DEV_IDE').
tape_type2tapevariable(ide_atapi, 'BLK_DEV_IDETAPE').
tape_type2tapevariable(scsi, 'CHR_DEV_ST').
tape_type2tapevariable(qic_02, 'QIC02_TAPE').
tape_type2tapevariable(ftape, 'FTAPE').

%-----
resolve.

network:-
    Name = 'netowrka dapter',
    ask_type_of_hardware(
        Name,
        net_type2netvariable),
    network_connection(Name).

net_type2netvariable('3c501', 'EL1').
net_type2netvariable('3c503', 'EL2').
net_type2netvariable('3c505', 'ELPLUS').
net_type2netvariable('3c507', 'EL16').
net_type2netvariable('3c509', 'EL3').
net_type2netvariable('3c592', 'VORTEX').
net_type2netvariable('3c595', 'VORTEX').

```

```

net_type2netvariable('3c597','VORTEX').
net_type2netvariable('at1500','LANCE').
net_type2netvariable('ne2100','LANCE').
net_type2netvariable('lance','LANCE').
net_type2netvariable('pcinet32','LANCE32').
net_type2netvariable('smc','NET_VENDOR_SMC').
net_type2netvariable('wd80x3','WD80x3').
net_type2netvariable('smc_ultra','ULTRA').
net_type2netvariable('smc9194','SMC9194').
net_type2netvariable('at1700','AT1700').
net_type2netvariable('e21xx','E2100').
net_type2netvariable('depca','DEPCA').
net_type2netvariable('de10x','DEPCA').
net_type2netvariable('de200','DEPCA').
net_type2netvariable('de201','DEPCA').
net_type2netvariable('de202','DEPCA').
net_type2netvariable('de422','DEPCA').
net_type2netvariable('de203','EWRK3').
net_type2netvariable('de204','EWRK3').
net_type2netvariable('de205','EWRK3').
net_type2netvariable('etherexpress','EEXPRESS').
net_type2netvariable('etherexpresspro','EEXPRESS_PRO').
net_type2netvariable('fmv_181','FMV18X').
net_type2netvariable('fmv_182','FMV18X').
net_type2netvariable('fmv_183','FMV18X').
net_type2netvariable('fmv_184','FMV18X').
net_type2netvariable('pclan_plus27247a','HPLAN_PLUS').
net_type2netvariable('pclan_plus27247b','HPLAN_PLUS').
net_type2netvariable('pclan_27245','HPLAN').
net_type2netvariable('pclan_27xxx','HPLAN').
net_type2netvariable('hp10','HP100').
net_type2netvariable('hp100vg','HP100').
net_type2netvariable('etherteam','ETH16I').
net_type2netvariable('ne2000','NE2000').
net_type2netvariable('ne1000','NE2000').
net_type2netvariable('ni5210','NI52').
net_type2netvariable('ni6510','NI65').
net_type2netvariable('seeq8005','SEEQ8005').
net_type2netvariable('sk_g16','SK_G16').
net_type2netvariable('ansel_comm_3200','AC3200').
net_type2netvariable('apricot','APRICOT').
net_type2netvariable('de425','DE4X5').
net_type2netvariable('de434','DE4X5').
net_type2netvariable('de435','DE4X5').
net_type2netvariable('de450','DE4X5').
net_type2netvariable('de500','DE4X5').
net_type2netvariable('dc21x4x','DEC_ELCP').
net_type2netvariable('digi','DGRS').
net_type2netvariable('zenith','ZNET').
net_type2netvariable('at_lan_tec_realtek','ATP').
net_type2netvariable('de600','DE600').
net_type2netvariable('ibm_tropic','IBMTR').
net_type2netvariable('defea','DEFXX').
net_type2netvariable('defpa','DEFXX').
net_type2netvariable('arc0e','ARCNET_ETH').
net_type2netvariable('arc0s','ARCNET_1051').
net_type2netvariable('isdn','ISDN').

network_connection(Name):-
    fflag(Name, y),
    ask_type_of_hardware(
        'network connection',
        net_connection_type2netvariable).

network_connection(_).

```

```

net_connection_type2netvariable('ppp','PPP').
net_connection_type2netvariable('slip','SLIP').
net_connection_type2netvariable('plip','PLIP').
net_connection_type2netvariable('dlci','DLCI').
net_connection_type2netvariable('sdlc','SDLC').
net_connection_type2netvariable('tcp_ip','INET').
net_connection_type2netvariable('radio_net','NET_RADIO').
net_connection_type2netvariable('baycom','BAYCOM').
net_connection_type2netvariable('strip','STRIP').
net_connection_type2netvariable('netrom','NETROM').
net_connection_type2netvariable('ax25','AX25').
net_connection_type2netvariable('appletalk','ATALK').
net_connection_type2netvariable('ipx','IPX_INTERN').

%----- MODEM -----
modem:-
    ask_type_of_hardware(
        'modem',
        serial_type2serial_variable).

serial_type2serial_variable( digiboard, 'DIGI').
serial_type2serial_variable( cyclades, 'CYCLADES').
serial_type2serial_variable( stallion, 'STALDRV').
serial_type2serial_variable( riscom8, 'RISCOM8').
serial_type2serial_variable( other, 'SERIAL').

%----- MOUSE -----
mouse:-
    ask_type_of_hardware(
        'mouse',
        mouse_type2mouse_variable).

mouse_type2mouse_variable( atixl, 'ATIXL_BUSMOUSE').
mouse_type2mouse_variable( logitech, 'BUSMOUSE').
mouse_type2mouse_variable( busmouse, 'BUSMOUSE').
mouse_type2mouse_variable( microsoft, 'MS_BUSMOUSE').
mouse_type2mouse_variable( ps_2, 'PSMOUSE').
mouse_type2mouse_variable( '82C710', '82C710_MOUSE').

%----- PRINTER -----
printer:-
    ask_type_of_hardware(
        'printer',
        printer_type2printer_variable).

printer_type2printer_variable( parallel, 'PRINTER').
printer_type2printer_variable( regular, 'PRINTER').

%-----

%-----
% ask_type_of_hardware/2 Provides uniform way to ask a user about hardware
% Installed on the system
%
ask_type_of_hardware(Name, Item):-
    !,nl,
    hw_type_general_help(Item, Name, 'just a list'),
    ask_type_of_hardware(Name, Item, 0).

```

```

ask_type_of_hardware(Name, Item, Count):-
    string_concat('What type is your computer ',Name, PromptBase0),
    string_concat( PromptBase0, ' #', PromptBase),
    string_concat( PromptBase, Count, Prompt),
    askTermD(Prompt, 'nomore', Type, hw_type_help(Item, Name)),
    aux_type_of_hardware(Name, Item, Count, Type)
    ;
    not fflag(quit, y).

aux_type_of_hardware(_, _, _, nomore).

aux_type_of_hardware(Name, Item, Count, Type):-
    Type \== nomore,
    Goal =.. [Item, Type, Var],
    Goal,
    (
        set_variable_value(Var, y),
        assert(fflag(Name, y)),
        NCount is Count + 1,
        ask_type_of_hardware(Name, Item, NCount)
    )
    ;
    not fflag(quit, y),
    writef('\7'),
    writef('\nWrong type!\n'),
    hw_type_help(Item, Name),
    ask_type_of_hardware(Name, Item, Count).

hw_type_help(Item, Name):-
    string_concat(Name, ' type you want info on', Prompt),
    askTermD( Prompt, 'just a list', Type),
    hw_type_general_help(Item, Name, Type).

hw_type_general_help(Item, Name, 'just a list'):-
    writef('The following types of %w are available\n', [Name]),
    retract(fflag(giving_help,_)),
    assert(fflag(giving_help,y)),
    Goal =.. [Item, Type, Var],
    bagof(Type, Var ^ Goal, List),
    retract(fflag(giving_help,_)),
    assert(fflag(giving_help,n)),
    write_ln(List).

hw_type_general_help(Item, Name, Type):-
    Type \== 'just a list',
    retract(fflag(giving_help,_)),
    assert(fflag(giving_help,y)),
    Goal =.. [Item, Type, Var],
    Goal,
    (
        variable(Var, _, Help, _, _),
        writef('%w : %w\n', [Type, Help]),
        retract(fflag(giving_help,_)),
        assert(fflag(giving_help,n))
    )
    ;
    retract(fflag(giving_help,_)),
    assert(fflag(giving_help,n)),
    not fflag(quit, y),
    writef('\7'),
    writef('\nWrong type!\n'),
    hw_type_help(Item, Name).

```

```

%-----
% Prompts user for a variable value.
% Returns typed value or default value if RETURN was pressed via Term
askTermD(Prompt, Default, Term):-
    !,
    askTermD(Prompt, Default, Term,0).

askTermD(Prompt, Default, Term, Help):-
    not fflag(quit, y),
    writef('%w [%w.](^D to abort): %f',[Prompt,Default]),
    peek_byte(Key),
    aux_askTermD(Key, Prompt, Default, Term, Help).

aux_askTermD(Key, Prompt, Default, Term, Help):-
    check_user_key(Key, Prompt, Default, Term, Help)
    ;
    not fflag(quit, y),
    read(Input),
    assign_default(Input, Default, Term).

% User accepts the default value
check_user_key(10, _, Default, Term, _):-
    skip(10),
    write(Default),
    assign_default(10, Default, Term).

% User typed '?' -- give him/her help
check_user_key(63, Prompt, Default, Term, 0):-
    skip(10),
    writef('No help available on this item\n'),
    askTermD(Prompt, Default, Term, 0).

check_user_key(63, Prompt, Default, Term, Help):-
    skip(10),
    Help \== 0,
    Help,
    askTermD(Prompt, Default, Term, Help).

check_user_key(-1,_,_,_):-
    retract_ifany(fflag(giving_help, _)),
    assert(fflag(quit, y)),
    writef('\n\7You pressed ^D -- aboring the interview\n'),
    pause,
    !,fail.

check_user_key(_,_,_,_):-
    fail.

%-----
% Assigns either default value if the 1st parameter and atom end_of_file, or
% any other value given in the 1st parameter
assign_default(end_of_file, Default, Default):-
    nl,
    !.

assign_default(10, Default, Default):-
    nl,
    !.

assign_default(Value, _, Value):-
    Value \== end_of_file,
    Value \== 10.

```

```

%-----

write_result:-
    askTermD('File to write configuration results to', 'config', OutFile),
    tell(OutFile),
    print_all_defined_vars,
    told,
    review_result(OutFile).

review_result(OutFile):-
    askTermD('Do you want to review the result ?', yes, If_review),
    (
    If_review \== yes
    ;
    string_concat('less ', OutFile, ShellCommand),
    shell(ShellCommand)
    ).

print_all_defined_vars:-
    variable(Name, _, _, Value),
    Value \== undefined,
    Value \== n,
    writef('CONFIG_%w=%w\n', [Name, Value]),
    fail.

print_all_defined_vars.

set_variable_value(Prefix, Suffix, Value):-
    string_concat(Prefix, Suffix, Name),
    set_variable_value( Name, Value).

set_variable_value(Name, Value):-
    retract(variable(Name, Type, Prompt, Default, _)),
    assert(variable(Name, Type, Prompt, Default, Value)).

shell_command:-
    askTermD('Command', 'just kidding', Command),
    !, Command \== 'just kidding',
    clear_screen,
    string_concat(Command, ' 2>&l |less', Command1),
    writef('Press "q" to return back\n'), pause,
    shell(Command1, _).

shell_comamnd.

```

A.2 Config2rules

```
#!/usr/bin/perl
#####
# NAME
#   $Id: //depot/home/beznosov/Classes/CEN5120/project/linux-kernel/input/config2rules#11$
#
# DESCRIPTION
#   Converts Config.in files in linux kernel source tree
#   (linux/arch/i386/config.in is a root) into a list of rules
#   for further processing by prolog based configurating
#   expert system.
#
# AUTHOR
#   Konstantin Beznosov (http://www.cs.fiu.edu/~beznosov)
#
# CREATION DATE
#   3/10/97
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#
#####

#####
#Options:
# -b use provided base instead of default one (/usr/src/linux) for
#   recursive parsing
# -d produce debug output on stderr
# -l print redundant dependencies
# -p produce output suitable for loading directly in Edinberg prolog engine.
#
#####

require 'getopts.pl';

Getopts('db:lp');

$base = '/usr/src/linux' unless $opt_b;

$glob_IF_var_is_on = 0;

$DEBUG = 1 if $opt_d;

if ($opt_p)
{
    &print_header;
    &define_prolog_predicates;
}

```

```

read_config_file(@ARGV[0] ? @ARGV[0] : "/usr/src/linux/arch/i386/config.in", 'fh00');

exit 0;

sub read_config_file {
# parsers config file

    local($filename, $input) = @_;
    $input++;
    print STDERR "Reading \"$filename\"\n" if $DEBUG;

    if ($opt_p)
    {
        print "%-----\n";
        print "% From file \"$filename\"\n";
        print "%-----\n";
        print "\n";
    }

    unless(open($input, "<$filename"))
    {
        print STDERR "Can't open file \"@[0]\": $!\n";
        return;
    }

    while (<$input>) {
        /(hex|int)\s+\s*(.*)\s+(\w+)\s+(\w+)/
        && print_hex_int_rule($1,$2,$3,$4);

        /bool +\s*(.*)\s+CONFIG_(\w+)/
        && print_bool_tristate_rule($1,$2,'b');

        /tristate +\s*(.*)\s+CONFIG_(\w+)/
        && print_bool_tristate_rule($1,$2,'t');

        /\s*if\s*\[\s*\s*\$CONFIG_(\w+)\s*\s*\(!{0,1}=\)\s*\s*(\w+)\s*\s*\]/
        && set_if_var("$1 $2 $3");

        /\s*if\s*\[\s*\s*\(!\s*\s*\$CONFIG_(\w+)\s*\s*\(!{0,1}=\)\s*\s*(\w+)\s*\s*\]/
        && set_if_var("$1 \!\$2 $3");

        /\s*if\s*\[\s*\s*\$CONFIG_(\w+)\s*\s*\(!{0,1}=\)\s*\s*(\w+)\s*\s*\s+\s*\s*\s+\s*\s*\$CONFIG_(\w+)\s*\s*\(!{0,1}=\)\s*\s*(\w+)\s*\s*\]/
        && set_if_var("$1 $2 $3 and \'$4\' $5 $6");

        /\s*if\s*\[\s*\s*\$CONFIG_(\w+)\s*\s*\(!{0,1}=\)\s*\s*(\w+)\s*\s*\s+\s*\s*\s+\s*\s*\$CONFIG_(\w+)\s*\s*\(!{0,1}=\)\s*\s*(\w+)\s*\s*\]/
        && set_if_var("$1 $2 $3 or \'$4\' $5 $6");

        /^\s*fi/
        && end_if();

        if (/^\s*source\s+([\w-\/\.]+)/)
        {
            read_config_file("$base/$1", $input);
            if ($opt_p)
            {
                print "%-----\n";
                print "% Back to file \"$filename\"\n";
                print "%-----\n";
                print "\n";
            }
        }
    }
}

close $input;

```

```

    print STDERR "Back from reading \"$filename\"\n" if $DEBUG;
    return;
}

sub print_bool_tristate_rule {
    if ($opt_p)
    {
        printf "variable(\`@[1]\`, @[2], \`@[0]\`, n, undefined )\n";
    }
    else
    {
        printf "%-25.25s|s| %-50.50s", @[1], @[2], @[0];
    }
    print_dependencies(@[1]);
}

sub print_hex_int_rule {
    if ($opt_p)
    {
        printf "variable(\`@[2]\`, @[0], \`@[1]\`, @[3], undefined )\n";
    }
    else
    {
        printf "%-25.25s|%1.1s| %-41.41s [%6.6s]", @[2], @[0], @[1], @[3];
    }
    print_dependencies(@[2]);
}

sub set_if_var {

    #local @old = grep(/@[0]/,@glob_IF_vars);
    #print STDERR "@[0] $#old $#glob_IF_vars @glob_IF_vars\n";
    #return if $#old > 0;

    $glob_IF_var_is_on++;

    if ($opt_p)
    {
        @[0] =~ s/!=/is_not/g;
        @[0] =~ s/=set_to/g;
        @[0] =~ s/^(S+)/\'$1\'; # Sarround variable with quotes
    }

    $glob_IF_vars[$glob_IF_var_is_on] = @[0];
    $#glob_IF_vars_values[$glob_IF_var_is_on] = "@[2] @[1]";

}

sub end_if {
    print STDERR "$glob_IF_var_is_on\n" if $glob_IF_var_is_on < 0;
    $glob_IF_vars[$glob_IF_var_is_on] = "";
    $glob_IF_var_is_on--;
}

sub print_dependencies
{
    local $variable = @[0];
    local $extra = 0;
    local $i;
    local $j;

    local $no_and = 1;

    if($opt_p)
    {
        print "if \'$variable\' is_wanted";
    }
}

```

```

}

# print dependencies
for ( $i = 1; $i <= $glob_IF_var_is_on ; $i++) {

    # Build a list of all dependencies for this current variable
    $glob_all_vars{$variable} .= " $glob_IF_vars[$i]";

    print STDERR "\nchecking $variable: $glob_all_vars{$variable}\n" if $DEBUG;

    $extra = 0;
    if ( !defined $opt_l ) # produce short dependencies lists
    {
        # Ignore those dependencies that can be inferred from any of
        # dependencies before

        # Go through all previous variables and make sure they are
        # not dependent on the current yet
        for ( $j = $glob_IF_var_is_on; $j > $i; $j-- )
        {
            print STDERR $glob_IF_vars[$j],$glob_IF_vars[$i], "\n" if $DEBUG;
            $extra = check4extra($glob_IF_vars[$i],$glob_IF_vars[$j]);
            last if $extra == 1; # do not check further since there
            # are already some extra dependencies
        }

    }

    next if $extra == 1;
    if ($opt_p)
    {
        printf " and $glob_IF_vars[$i]";
    }
    else
    {
        print " | $glob_IF_vars[$i]";
    }
}

if ($opt_p)
{
    printf " then \'$variable\'.\n";
}
else
{
    print " | $glob_IF_vars[$i]";
}

print "\n";
}

sub check4extra
# Checks if new depends on old already.
# check4extra(old,new)
{
    @_ [0] =~ /(\w+)/;
    local $old = $1;

    @_ [1] =~ /(\w+)/;
    local $new = $1;

    local @list = split(' ', $glob_all_vars{$new});

```

```
print STDERR "new var $new depends on: ", join(' ',@list),"\n" if $DEBUG;

local @result = grep(/$old/,@list);
print STDERR "$new depends on $old: $glob_all_vars{$new} : $#result\n" if $DEBUG;
return ($#result >= 0) ? 1 : 0;

}
#####
#
sub define_prolog_predicates
{
    print
    "
";

}
#####
#
sub print_header
{
    require 'ctime.pl';
    $today = ctime(time);
print
"% File was generated on $today
";

}
}
```

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